

ELECTROCHEMICAL SENSOR FABRICATED BY LASER SCRIBED GRAPHENE MODIFIED WITH NAFION® AND TiO₂:05Au NANOPARTICLES FOR ESTRIOLE DETERMINATION

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Resumo

Estríol (E3) is an important endogenous hormone that belongs to the group of steroid estrogens. In non-pregnant women, its presence is relatively low, and it does not act as the predominant estrogen. However, during pregnancy, E3 is produced in large quantities through the feto-placental pathway, contributing to 90% of total circulating estrogens during gestation. The presence of E3 is closely related to gestational health, making it an important biomarker for monitoring fetal health, given that low levels of E3 are associated with gestational and fetal complications. Currently, the most common analytical methods to determine E3 in biological fluids include immunoassays, electrophoresis, and chromatographic techniques. However, these techniques require sophisticated instrumentation, highly trained personnel, and lengthy analysis times. The use of miniaturized electrochemical sensors offers several advantages, such as low reagent consumption and short analysis times. The fabrication of these sensors using laser scribed graphene (LSG) allows for scalable, rapid, and less laborious manufacturing, favoring the sensor development process. In this work, an electrochemical sensor fabricated by LSG on a polyimide substrate was developed for the determination of E3 in human biological fluids. The modification of the working electrode was evaluated with different modifiers, and it was found that using a combination of Nafion® and TiO₂:05Au nanoparticles improve significantly the analytical response to E3, by about 93% compared to the unmodified sensor, suggesting a synergistic effect between nanoparticles and Nafion® membrane. The optimal concentration of Nafion® to be used was also evaluated and determined to be 2%, as well as the pre-concentration time, which was fixed as 120 s. The scan rate study allowed visualizing that the mass transport process is mixed, diffusional and adsorptive, indicating that the pre-concentration effect possibly occurs on the surface of LSG/Nafion®/TiO₂:05Au. Additionally, pH evaluation showed that pH 2 presented the best analytical response and also indicated that the molecule is proton-dependent. For quantitative purposes, pulse techniques, square wave voltammetry (SWV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) were evaluated, where it was found that DPV presents a better analytical response and more defined oxidation peaks, being chosen for next steps. Characterizations by Raman vibration spectroscopy and FT-IR allowed visualizing that the surface of the proposed sensor approaches reduced graphene oxide (rGO). Subsequent steps are based on the construction of the analytical curve, as well as the performance of assays on real samples, stability studies and interference tests.

Palavras-chave: Electroanalytical, Miniaturized sensor, Hormone

Categoria: Trabalho desenvolvido na Pós-Graduação

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